

2035, dull 2077, and IR36. Lysine per seed was highest in dull 2035, followed by dull 2077, dull EM47 and ae and IR36. Fat content was high in sugary and shrunken grains.

All mutants except ae had lower

apparent amylose content in brown rice than IR36. Gelatinization temperature (GT) of the samples were intermediate except for dull EM47 and ae.

The extremely high GT value for the sugary mutant may be due to the effect

of its high sucrose level on GT.

Corresponding starch mutants based on Kinmaze showed similar trends in starch properties. A sample of the ae mutant of Kinmaze had 31 % apparent amylose in defatted brown rice. □

Quality characteristics of some new aromatic rices

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We compared milling and cooking performance of 13 aromatic rice lines and Basmati 370. All samples were

grown under similar environmental conditions and tested 2 mo after hand harvesting.

Brown rice recovery varied widely (see table). All lines except NIRRI-PTB-11 and NIRRI-PTB-138 (PL) had higher brown rice yields than Basmati 370; NIRRI-PTB-22 had the highest yield. Head rice yield of NIRRI-PTB-22 was also highest. NIRRI-PTB-140 had more

than 40% broken. NIRRI-1-10643-1-65 had exceptionally long grains. Three lines had higher length:breadth ratios (L/B) than Basmati 370. Six lines had amylose as high as or higher than that of Basmati 370.

Cooked NIRRI-PTB-140-6 had the highest LB, followed by NIRRI-PTB-138 (PL). The elongation ratio of S41 was higher than that of Basmati 370. □

Milling and cooking characteristics of some aromatic rices. Ludhiana, India.

Variety or line	Milling recovery (% of rough rice)			Milled rice					
	Brown rice	Milled rice	Head rice	Protein (%)	Amylose (%)	Length of raw rice (mm)	Length:breadth		Elongation ratio ^a
							Raw rice	Cooked rice	
NIRRI-PTB-11	76.1	70.0	55.0	9.7	21.7	6.7	3.94	3.88	1.45
NIRRI-PTB-20	78.3	72.0	47.0	8.5	26.3	6.7	3.53	3.36	1.25
NIRRI-PTB-22	80.4	74.0	64.2	9.2	19.9	6.8	3.40	3.60	1.32
NIRRI-PTB-23	78.4	72.1	55.7	8.8	19.0	6.6	3.88	3.64	1.38
NIRRI-PTB-36	79.9	73.5	41.9	9.4	24.5	6.7	3.19	3.58	1.39
NIRRI-PTB-138 (PL)	77.5	71.3	47.7	9.8	18.1	7.7	4.05	4.42	1.38
NIRRI-PTB-138 (MS)	74.7	68.7	50.8	8.3	17.2	7.5	3.95	3.75	1.20
NIRRI-PTB-140	78.9	72.6	32.5	9.6	16.3	7.5	4.17	4.21	1.35
NIRRI-PTB-140-6	78.8	72.5	54.1	9.6	15.4	7.9	4.65	4.50	1.37
NIRRI-PTB-145	80.2	73.8	54.6	10.2	12.7	7.3	4.29	3.88	1.38
NIRRI-PTB-170	79.4	73.0	47.8	9.4	18.1	6.9	3.29	3.76	1.36
S41	79.9	73.5	43.5	9.0	19.0	7.0	3.89	4.07	1.57
NIRRI-1-106-4-3-1-65	79.5	73.1	48.7	8.4	18.1	8.3	4.61	4.03	1.46
Basmati 370	78.0	71.7	42.6	9.8	19.0	7.7	4.28	4.37	1.53
Mean	78.6	72.2	49.4	9.3	18.9	7.2	3.97	3.93	1.39

^aLength of cooked milled rice ÷ length of raw rice.

Disease resistance

Sources of multiple resistance to rice blast (BI) and bacterial blight (BB) in Nepal

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Rice BI caused by *Pyricularia oryzae*

and BB caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* have been observed widely in the tropical and subtropical regions of Nepal, the country's major rice-producing areas. Breeding for varieties with multiple resistance to these diseases would be easier and quicker using sources with multiple resistance.

To identify such sources, varietal reactions to BI and BB in Kankai,

Sources of multiple resistance to rice BI and BB in Nepal, 1985-87.^a

Variety	Reaction to BI		Reaction to BB	
	Average	Range	Average	Range
Janaki	2.3	0.0-3.0	1.5	0.0-3.0
Laxmi	2.1	0.0-3.0	2.4	1.5-3.0
KAU1727	1.7	0.0-3.0	3.1	3.0-3.4

^aScoring according to *Standard evaluation system for rice* scale: 0-9. ^bScored 21 d after inoculation.

Tarahara, Parwanipur, Rampur, and Surkhet screening nurseries in 1985-87 were reviewed.

In the tests, 848 entries were evaluated for BI resistance and 644 for BB

resistance: 366 (43.2%) were resistant to BI and 61 (9.5%) to BB. Of these, 13 lines/varieties had resistance to both diseases.

Janaki, Laxmi, and KAU1727

showed high field resistance to both pathogens at all sites (see table) and might be useful parental materials. Janaki and Laxmi are released varieties. □

Resistance of upland rice varieties to pale yellow mottle virus (PYMV) disease in Sierra Leone

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PYMV disease occurs sporadically in Sierra Leone, and its incidence is increasing. Several plots in the eastern and northern provinces have had fairly high levels of infection, and the potential for considerable yield loss is high.

We tested eight released varieties and promising lines for resistance to PYMV under upland conditions at Kenema in the eastern province. Varieties were sown in 10-m² plots in a randomized complete block design with 4 replications. One set of varieties was inoculated 3 wk after seeding with sap from blended infected leaves. One set was not inoculated. All treatments received standard fertilizer application and cultural management.

ROK16 was resistant to the virus;

Response of 8 rice cultivars to inoculation with pale yellow mottle virus disease. Sierra Leone, 1983-84 wet season.

Treatment	Mean yield (t/ha)	Yield loss (%)	Mean height (cm)	Stunting (%)	Reaction ^a
ROK16	2.9		112		
ROK16 + virus	2.7	9	110	1.8	R
Lac 23	2.3		112		
Lac 23 + virus	1.1	54	106	5.4	I
ROK3	2.2		124		
ROK3 + virus	0.3	88	96	22.6	S
Tox 502-SLR	1.7		112		
Tox 502-SLR + virus	1.4	19	104	7.1	I
PN623-3	2.4		110		
PN623-3 + virus	0.3	88	70	36.4	S
IRAT8	1.6		93		
IRAT8 + virus	1.3	20	78	16	I
Tox 516-12-SLR	2.8		65		
Tox 516-12-SLR +virus	0.4	84	42	35.4	S
ROK15	2.9		109		
ROK15 + virus	0.1	97	74	32.1	S
LSD (0.05)	522		10		
CV (%)	19.3		6.4		

^aR = resistant: no infection, or faint and barely discernible leaf mottling. I = intermediate: mild leaf streaking or mottling with or without stunting. S = susceptible: evident chlorosis and leaf mottling with mild to severe stunting.

Tox 502-SLR, IRAT8, and Lac 23 gave intermediate responses (see table).

Despite its intermediate rating, Lac 23 had a significant yield reduction (54%).

PN623-3, Tox 516-12-SLR, ROK3, and ROK15, all rated as susceptible, gave significant yield reductions (84-97%).□

Development of a japonica rice variety with blast (BI) and bacterial blight (BB) resistance

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Resistances to BI and BB are not as strong in japonica rice varieties as in indica varieties. We used indica variety Tetep and japonica variety Toride 1 as BI-resistant parents and made crosses with traditional high-yielding japonica variety Aijing 23 that has BB resistance.

Japonica variety Chengte 232 derived

from Aijing 231/Ailoqing/Toride 1///Aijing 23//Nonghong 23/Tetep has been released. In artificial inoculation tests, it was resistant or moderately resistant to 13 of 14 local strong *Pyricularia oryzae* isolates and 5 *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* races (Table 1). It has 139-d duration in

Table 1. Reaction^a of Chengte 232 to 14 *P. oryzae* isolates and *S. campestris* pv. *oryzae* races. Hangzhou, China.

Variety	Reaction ^b to BI														Reaction ^b to BB				
	A1	A61	A63	B1	B15	C3	C13	C15	D1	D3	E1	E3	F1	G1	188	186	98	35	149
Chengte 232	R	R	R	MR	R	R	MR	R	R	MR	R	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
Nonghu 6	S	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	MR	MR	R
Tetep	S	R	S	R	R	S	R	R	R	R	MR	R	R	R					
Aijing 23	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	MR	MR	R	R	R

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible. ^bGrouping or race number based on Chinese differentials.